

STYLISTICS OF LANGUAGE AND SPEECH

Inomkhujaeva Shodiyakhon Abdukhodirkhuja qizi

BEAP tutor at Westminster International University in Tashkent

ishodiya@mail.ru<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8405829>

Annotation: Stylistics - is a science, a branch of linguistics, investigating principles and the results of selection and use of lexical, grammatical, phonetic and other language means for the transfer of thoughts and emotions under different circumstances of communication. In dealing with the objectives of stylistics one should mention its close interrelations with other sciences and disciplines such as theory of information, literature criticism, psychology, logic and even to some extent statistics.

Key words: stylistics, objects, word, language, level-oriented perspective

Stylistics is the "soul" of any developed language. Our thoughts are in the form of sentences or phrases the laws of the language we speak. These sentences are number theoretically infinite - consist of words expressing certain concepts about the objects and phenomena of the world around us of reality. On the specific stages of language development, the number of words is limited by our knowledge about objects, phenomena and their relationships. Therefore, it is usually assumed that the words of a particular language can be counted. According to some reports, developed European languages already have about a million words. Average a statistical native speaker of Russian, for example, usually uses a very limited vocabulary (the entire vocabulary of works A.S. Pushkin, according to scientists, is "only" 21,000 words). But the main thing, of course, is not how many words we know, but how skillfully they we use to express our thoughts.(Alekseyev)

Language is a social phenomenon, a product of society. It is born, lives develops and dies with society. Language is a mirror of the development of society and is qualitatively different at different stages of its evolution. Therefore, being still at a primitive stage of its development, preserving the primitive communal organizational structure of society, a person did not need variety of words and their connections, which is necessary for a civilized to a person(Alekseyev). After all, a word is a reflection of a "piece" of material reality, it names objects, phenomena, processes and connections between them. Therefore, the language of any people is determined by the level of its development. But there has never been and probably never will be a case where a particular language "lagged behind" or "overtook" spiritual, socio-economic and other the needs of the people who speak it.

When we use a word to denote necessary things, processes or connections, we do not think about how many words we need for embodiment of thoughts. We are also not interested in what words are made of, that we speak or write. But if you pay special attention on this question, then everyone will easily determine that words consist of frequently repeated small segments - morphemes. According to their roles in language and purpose, they differ from each other, forming special classes. Morphemes in the language, of course, are much smaller than words. And quite the number of units that form morphemes, that is, phonemes, is negligible. Though the number of phonemes and letters, that is, the symbols that denote the letter phonemes, often does not match in different languages (usually there are more phonemes than letters), this discrepancy is not so significant. And now, having in his three or

four dozen phonemes at our disposal, we not only express everything that it is necessary to say, but we also laugh and weep, we admire and are annoyed, that is, expressing our emotions. This is possible only thanks to the amazing flexibility, mobility, capacity of the “bricks” or units that make up our language main linguistic levels.

Issues with stylistic research Traditional branches of linguistics such as phonetics, which studies speech sounds and intonation; lexicology, which studies words, their meaning, and vocabulary structure; and grammar, which studies the forms of words and their function in a sentence, which is examined by syntax. These fields of linguistic study are well-defined and have a long history of looking at language issues from a level-oriented perspective. As a result, the subject matter and material under study in these linguistic disciplines are quite straightforward. When we talk about stylistics, things get a little more tricky. According to some researchers, this is a relatively new discipline of linguistics, with only a few decades of intensive linguistic study. It was only recently that the term stylistics was coined. In truth, the scope of difficulties and the subject of stylistic study can be traced back to ancient rhetorical and poetical schools.(Znamenskaya)

The issue that makes the concept of stylistics so perplexing has to do with both the object and the subject of study. We cannot proceed from the level-biased approach that is so logically stated through the hierarchical system of sounds, words, and phrases when we speak of the stylistic value of a text. Not only may each of these linguistic pieces be assigned a stylistic meaning, but so can their interactions, as well as the structure and composition of the entire text.(Znamenskaya)

References:

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